

IMPROVED COVID-19 KNOWLEDGE AND CONSCIOUSNESS AMONG RESIDENTS OF ABAKALIKI: UNDERSTANDING THE ROLE OF MEDIA CAMPAIGNS

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Abstract: The Coronavirus is a large family of viruses known to cause illnesses ranging from the common cold to acute respiratory tract infection. The severity of the infection may be visible as pneumonia, acute respiratory syndrome, and even death. The mortality rate is not only high, but threatens our existence as a people. One of the tasks of the mass media is the promotion of knowledge on health issues; inform and educate members of the society. So far, media campaigns have been deployed across board to manage the spread of this deadly virus. It was against this backdrop that this study was initiated to appraise the influence of these campaigns against COVID-19 virus. Explanatory mixed method research design was adopted, so as to empirically confirm, cross-validate, or corroborate findings of the research. A representative sample size of 385 was studied. Results indicate that most Nigerians, particularly in the Abakaliki, now have a detailed knowledge of the COVID-19 virus, its transmission and prevention methods as well as the medical anthropology. And there's a correlation between their level of exposure to COVID-19 campaigns and knowledge. It is therefore imperative to note that media campaigns can effectively help in managing the spread of diseases. We recommend among others, that there should be sustained media campaigns against COVID-19 so that people can continue to maintain their adopted simple personal hygiene practices.

Keywords: Media Campaign, Attitudes, Behavior, COVID-19, Disease Outbreak

Introduction

Over the years, Nigeria have continued to experience deadly health challenges, ranging from Polio, bird-flu, HIV/AIDS, Ebola, Lassa Fever to this recent ravaging Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic. This virus has negatively affected the health, economic and socio-political aspects of the country and the wellbeing of her population, leading to the death of so many people.

Recognizing the deadly nature of the virus, individuals and nations have in addition to other remedial controls taken several measures through mass media campaigns to avoid being infected. This response is in recognition of the important role of the mass media as a tool for

public health education and enlightenment and its potency in triggering behavioral or attitudinal change. With the entry of the COVID-19 in Nigeria, the surveillance function of the media was called to the front burner through several awareness campaigns.

The mass media as a social driver for human and social development undoubtedly played a critical role in this regard (Asemah, 2011, p.23). They mostly determined what we do and how we do them especially as it regards our safety culture and tracing patients. Unarguably, bringing a lot of social changes through awareness in most parts of the world. No doubt, media communication has powers to change people's behavior or attitude and

persuade them to take up a particular course of action. In most cases, it can persuade people to do what they never wanted to do before (Okunna, 1999, p.210). Its agenda setting function explains better how it influences people on what to think about.

Since the mass media occupy a privileged position and also have as their social responsibility the duty to inform the consciousness of the general public on the outbreak diseases in the society, one expects it to perform these roles effectively to avoid blames from the public (Obot, 2012, p.489). Creating adequate public health awareness among the people is an essential step aimed at reducing its potency. Therefore, one can boldly say that mass media is the fundamental platform in creating public health awareness. According to Olujimi and Adekunle (2010, p.230) information is the gateway to the public health. Mass media plays an important role in combating the spread of viruses and mitigating its health and social impact. This is in line with the mass media's cardinal responsibilities which amongst others are to inform, educate and mobilize people for action through a well-planned media campaign, with clear messages. This awareness can be created to positively influence attitude and ultimately engender proper behavior. In the case of COVID-19, the media are no doubt very essential. As channels with capacity to simultaneously reach larger, heterogeneous, and diversified audience, the media are fundamental in raising the awareness/knowledge level of the public and heralding the desired compliance among the people.

As the presence of this dangerous disease, continues to ravage the world, the surveillance function of the media has been called to the front burner through several campaigns. This prompted the Pan African Health Organisation in collaboration with the World Health Organisation to encourage the national health authorities to engage the media for the delivery and dissemination of health messages to the population about the modes of transmission, prevention techniques, vaccines and clinical signs of COVID-19.

COVID-19 is transmitted to humans through contact with infected animals or people. This necessitates the need for more awareness through the media by floating campaign messages against this dreaded disease. In the fight against this deadly virus, the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) officials introduced the dissemination of information about the disease and its transmission prevention via churches and rural community radio awareness broadcastings and public informative posters and door-to-door education. This media campaign strategy has also been seriously used around the world.

Since the outbreak of this deadly virus in Nigeria, the media have been utilized to combat the virus, especially the broadcast media radio and TV which have been used to disseminate information against the spread of the virus. The federal, state, local governments and non-governmental organisations all attested to have massively used the media to raise public health awareness and engender the desired behavioural change among the public with regards to the COVID-19. However, the concern here is whether these roles of the media in the campaigns against COVID-19 outbreak in Nigeria engender development and engineered any behavioural change.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria and, indeed, many countries in Africa, the mass media are the major channels of communicating health information to both urban and rural dwellers. In a bid to prevent and control eradicate the COVID-19 disease, media organizations embarked on a massive awareness and sensitization campaigns to arouse national consciousness about its prevalence and fatality. The outbreak of this deadly disease has brought in its wake far-reaching social, economic, security and health consequences on both the citizens and the nation.

This outbreak brings to the fore, the poor personal and environmental hygiene culture among the people irrespective of the media campaigns against it. The media is supposed to be influential in its societal task and

roles of curbing the escalation of the virus i.e., the surveillance function of the media in the society.

This study aims to explore how COVID-19 media campaigns influenced people's attitude and behaviors in Abakiliki, Ebonyi State. Notwithstanding the intended seeming influence and advantages of the media campaigns with regard to improved health, critics seem to see media campaigns as mere propaganda tools in the hands of the owners' thus hoist issues that border on credibility. Therefore, raising doubtful questions on whether the media campaigns really influences the people as it regards the campaigns against COVID-19. They even argue and contend that interpersonal communication are more credible platforms for advocating for attitudinal and behavioral change. This study, therefore, would help ascertain in empirical terms, the developmental roles of the media in the campaigns against COVID-19 outbreak with regard to improving the health and living standards of the people.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of the study is to examine the developmental Role of the media in the Campaign against COVID-19 Outbreak in Nigeria. Other specific objectives of the study are:

- i. To ascertain the exposure level of Abakiliki residents to the media campaigns against COVID-19 outbreak.
- ii. To examine the extent to which the media messages on COVID-19 influenced the knowledge of Abakiliki residents on the virus.
- iii. To ascertain the level at which the media messages on COVID-19 influenced the attitudes of Abakiliki residents toward the virus.
- iv. To determine the extent to which the media messages on COVID-19 Virus Disease influenced the behaviours of the Abakiliki residents regarding the virus

Research Hypotheses

This study is guided by the alternate hypotheses below:

1. **H_i:** There is a significant relationship between the frequency of Abakiliki residents' exposure to media

messages on COVID-19 outbreak and their knowledge of the symptoms of the virus.

2. **H_i:** There is a significant relationship between the Abakiliki' residents' positive knowledge toward the COVID-19 Virus and their positive attitude.

3. **H_i:** There is a significant relationship between the Abakiliki residents' positive attitude towards the COVID-19 virus and their positive practice.

Literature Review

The Development Perspectives of Communication

Communication is central to the process of development, to the extent that the dependence of one on the other has virtually been taken for granted. To properly understand this relationship between the two concepts of communication and development, it is important to put in context the role of communication in the actualization of the process of development.

According to Okenwa (2002), "The development media theory stipulates that the media must of necessity, be involved in the business of development: not just ordinarily, but being in the forefront of development, to the extent of determining the pace of development. In other words the pace of development would to a large extent be determined not just by the extent to which the media are used. Media exposure, media access and media use are three distinct variables that can guarantee media impact which is at the very heart of development.

An Overview of COVID-19

COVID-19 is a family of viruses with a positive-sense RNA that possess an outer viral coat. This family of viruses mainly cause respiratory diseases in humans, in the forms of common cold or pneumonia as well as respiratory infections. Up until the year 2003, coronavirus (CoV) had attracted limited interest from researchers. However, after the SARS (severe acute respiratory syndrome) outbreak caused by the SARS-CoV, the coronavirus was looked at with renewed interest. This also happened to be the first epidemic of the 21st century originating in the Guangdong province of China. Almost 10 years later, there was a MERS (Middle East respiratory syndrome) outbreak in 2012,

which was caused by the MERS-CoV. Both SARS and MERS have a zoonotic origin and originated from bats. A unique feature of these viruses is the ability to mutate rapidly and adapt to a new host. The zoonotic origin of these viruses allows them to jump from host to host. Coronaviruses are known to use the angiotensin-converting enzyme-2 (ACE-2) receptor or the dipeptidyl peptidase IV (DPP-4) protein to gain entry into cells for replication. On December 2019, almost seven years after the MERS 2012 outbreak, a novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) surfaced in Wuhan in the Hubei region of China. The outbreak rapidly grew and spread to neighboring countries. However, rapid communication of information and the increasing scale of events led to quick quarantine and screening of travelers, thus containing the spread of the infection. The major part of the infection was restricted to China, and a second cluster was found on a cruise ship called the Diamond Princess docked in Japan. It was identified as novel Coronavirus and was thus initially named 2019-nCoV; later, it was renamed severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), and the disease it causes is now referred to as Coronavirus Disease-2019 (COVID-19) by the WHO. However, it later became a global pandemic affecting about 462 million people with over 6 million mortality (WHO, 2022). It spreads through the nose or mouth of an infected person when they breathe, sneeze, cough, or speak. Affected persons experience respiratory illness and can recuperate without special care or treatment. But, older or people with underlying medical conditions becomes very ill requiring serious medical care or die. The best preventive measure to reduce or stop its transmission is to be knowledgeable about the virus and in what way it spreads. This can be done through media campaigns to reach a larger audience in the least possible time. People are supposed to stay safe by wearing nose masks, regularly washing their hands with soap and water or alcoholic based solution and staying at least one meter (1m) apart from others.

Prevention

The WHO has recommended that simple personal hygiene practices can be sufficient for the prevention of spread and containment of the disease. Practices such as frequent washing of soiled hands or the use of sanitizer for unsoiled hands help reduce transmission. Covering of mouth while sneezing and coughing, and disinfection of surfaces that are frequently touched, such as tabletops, doorknobs, and switches with 70% isopropyl alcohol or other disinfectants are broadly recommended. It is recommended that all individuals afflicted by the disease, as well as those caring for the infected, wear a mask to avoid transmission. Healthcare workers are advised to wear a complete set of personal protective equipment as per WHO-provided guidelines. Fumigation of dormitories, quarantine rooms, and washing of clothes and other fomites with detergent and warm water can help get rid of the virus. Parcels and goods are not known to transmit the virus, as per information provided by the WHO, since the virus is not able to survive sufficiently in an open, exposed environment. Quarantine of infected individuals and those who have come into contact with an infected individual is necessary to further prevent transmission of the virus. Quarantine is an age-old archaic practice that continues to hold relevance even today for disease containment. With the quarantine being implemented on such a large scale in some countries, taking the form of a national lockdown, the question arises of its impact on the mental health of all individuals. The prevention of the disease with the use of a vaccine is a more viable solution.

COVID-19 affects different people in different ways. Most infected people will develop mild to moderate illness and recover without hospitalization.

Most common symptoms:

- fever
- cough
- tiredness
- loss of taste or smell.

Less common symptoms:

- sore throat
- headache
- aches and pains
- diarrhoea
- a rash on skin, or discolouration **of fingers or toes**

toes

- red or irritated eyes.

Serious symptoms:

- difficulty breathing or shortness of breath
- loss of speech or mobility, or confusion
- chest pain.

Seek immediate medical attention if you have serious symptoms. Always call before visiting your doctor or health facility. People with mild symptoms who are otherwise healthy should manage their symptoms at home. On average it takes 5–6 days from when someone is infected with the virus for symptoms to show, however it can take up to 14 days.

Media Transmission of Health Messages

One of the tasks of the mass media is the promotion of knowledge on health issues. In discharging this duty, the mass media inform and educate members of the society on different health issues such as COVID-19 and many other health issues. Grilli, Ramsay, Minozzi, (2002, p.2) indicated that emphasis on consumerism in the delivery of healthcare highlights the potentially important role of mass media in increasing the public awareness and promoting the utilization of effective and efficient health services. The media play a crucial role in promoting the knowledge of people on issues of health as well as shaping their understanding of medicine and science in general (Moyer, 1995, p. 147 161) cited in (Diedong, 2013, p.47). Similarly, Weng (2014, p.4) asserts that mass media dissemination of health messages is very essential in shaping public knowledge and understanding of health issues.

As days come and go, the world continues to witness the outbreak of deadly diseases that herald severe health problems across the globe. There are so many health problems ravaging many parts of the world. Some of

them are COVID-19, cancer, malaria, tuberculosis, leprosy, HIV/AIDS, and Lassa fever. These health challenges have continued to deform and handicap lots of people while many have died via the contraction of these diseases. Hence, the need to adequately combat these health challenges is inevitable.

One very cardinal step in the process of combating the various health problems across the globe is the transmission of relevant health messages to the public. The Radio is very expedient in this regard. Okorie (2014, para. 7) aptly notes that;

The Radio are generally regarded as channels of communication that are capable of reaching heterogeneous audiences simultaneously with uniform messages. They (Radio) regularly cover all sorts of issues such as health, music, fine art, crime, sports, and political events (Meyer, 2002; Soola, 2004). The Radio transmit ideas and new information to target audience in the society. Tosanwumi (1994) has observed that the Radio educate, inform, and entertain. Beyond these functions, they also persuade and catalyze social mobilization. In other words, the Radio can be regarded as powerful sources of information because they have the capability to penetrate every segment of the society. They have the ability to disseminate messages about issues, ideals and products. Furthermore, the Radio have the capacity to create awareness and knowledge about issues of national interest.

Research has shown that media's dissemination of health information is important in shaping public beliefs and possibly behavior". In our society that relies on effective and efficient communication, the media play a major role in informing multiple aspects of individuals' lives, including their access to health information. Traditionally, public health organizations have used print and radio media and social marketing frameworks to disseminate important health messages to the public. In the past few decades, electronic media have stepped to the forefront of communication, and public health communication has evolved to reflect this (Newbold and Campos, 2011, p.5).

In today's media rich landscape, and especially with the advancements of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), increasing efforts are underway to incorporate Radio strategies into health education, promotion, and disease prevention practices (Melanie, Wakefield and Hornik 2010, Parker and Thorson 2009, Viswanath, Wallington and Blake 2009). At the same time, scholars have documented Radio's reach to select audiences and specific, limited, and moderate effects in influencing health knowledge, attitude, and behavior (Atkin 2001, Rice and Atkin 2009, Atkin and Salmon 2010, Salmon and Atkin 2003). To fully realize Radio's role in facilitating the pursuit of health education and promotion, and disease prevention, health communicators need to exploit multiple Radio and interactive digital media channels and carry out carefully planned media strategies to reach intended audiences (Ahmed and Bates, 2013, p3-4).

The responsibilities of the media are, amongst others, to disseminate health information and to frequently cover health-related topics and, as such, the media are the leading source of information about important health issues for many individuals. Media coverage of health-related events has become so important that several surveillance systems now rely on active trolling of internet news media to detect emerging disease threats. It is a relatively inexpensive way of exposing the population to information regarding their health and has the potential to reach a large proportion of the population, particularly groups that may be difficult to access through more traditional approaches. In the transmission of health messages, the radio deploy different approaches. The approaches are the straight news reports, drama presentations, interview/discussion and phone-in programmes, documentaries, features and opinion articles, cartoons, paid/public service announcements, news commentaries, editorials, etc. These approaches are used by the Radio to maximally communicate relevant health messages for public safety. Giving credence to this assertion, Daniel (2013, p.19) avers thus;

According to Catalán-Matamoros, (2011, p.400), there are four important things the media must do in transmitting health messages. They are;

1. Mobilizing and supporting local agencies and professionals who have direct access to individuals within the target population.
2. Bringing together partnerships of public, voluntary and private sector bodies and professional organizations.
3. Informing and educating the public, but also setting the agenda for public debate about the health topic, thereby modifying the climate of opinion surrounding it.
4. Encouraging local and national policy changes so as to create a supportive environment within which people are more able to change their behavior.

Theoretical Framework

To give this study a theoretical backing, this study was anchored on attitude-change theory. This theory is considered suitable to this study because it help to draw more light in to the theme of this study.

Attitude-Change Theory

The Attitude Change Theory was developed from propaganda theories in the 1930s during World War II (Baran & Davis, 2012, p. 175). The theory explains that there are pre-existing attitudes, whether biological or psychological which have to be changed if selected messages must have any effect on the target audience. Again, it explains that these pre-existing attitudes are core and therefore stand as barriers to effective penetration of messages for desired change. Thus an intellectual and emotional strategy of communication will influence change if properly channeled to do so. Change in evaluations and perceptions of an individual's predispositions will take place if the required modification favours his expectations, if it is tied to someone he admires, or if it is bound to be beneficial to him (Wood, 2000, p.539).

This theory explains three bases for attitude change, which include compliance, identification, and

internalization. These three processes demonstrate the different levels of attitude change (Wood, 2000, p.539).

In the campaign against COVID-19, possible barriers to knowledge acquisition, positive attitude and practice of campaign messages may include psychological, emotional and physical. Psychological when the people find it difficult to open up when they detect or observe some symptoms, due to shyness, stigmatization, cultural beliefs or religious beliefs. Physical, when screening and treatment facilities are not reachable or available, or medical specialists are limited. Emotional, when the fear of being diagnosed of the virus overrides the need for early detection. For the COVID-19 media campaign messages to effectively enhance knowledge, herald positive attitude and ultimately engender the desired behaviour towards the virus, the media messages must therefore be structured in such manner that these obstacles to effective communication are surmounted which will consequently herald the desired change among the people.

Methodology

To effectively evaluate the developmental roles of the media in the campaigns against COVID-19 outbreak in Nigeria, the researchers adopted the use of explanatory mixed method research design in this study. The approach enabled the researcher to generate both quantitative and qualitative data and generalize the results on the entire population. Another rationale for this approach, according to Creswell (2002, p 565) is that “one data collection form, supplies strengths to offset the weakness of the other form” with this design, the researcher gathered both quantitative and qualitative data, compared results from the analysis of both data and made statistical interpretations. The cross-sectional survey method was used to generate quantitative data while in-depth interview was used to generate qualitative data.

The population of the study is the entire residents of Abakaliki in Ebonyi state, Nigeria. The total population for the study is **199729** based on the statistics obtained from National Population Commission cited in National Bureau of Statistics 2016 projection figure (Annual Abstract of Statistics, 2016).

The researchers adopted the Australian National Statistical Service (NSS) online sampling Calculator, which is widely used by both social science and physical science researchers in Europe and parts of Asia. In this segment, the researchers opted for the selection of a manageable and representative sample size that would produce valid results because of the largeness of the population (**199,729**). A sample of 385 was drawn using online sample size calculator, with confidence level of 95% and confidence interval of 5.0%. The sample size for this study is **385** respondents.

Interview Session: Fifteen interviewees were purposively selected in Abakaliki metropolis for the interview session. So in all, the researchers interviewed fifteen respondents who were randomly selected to generate the required data for the study among the residents of Abakaliki.

Methods of Data Presentation and Analysis

The quantitative data generated from the use of questionnaire were presented using simple frequency distribution tables, percentages and numbers to ascertain the roles of the media in the campaigns against COVID-19 outbreak in Nigeria.

The qualitative data generated through in-depth interview were used to complement the quantitative data generated through questionnaire. The chi-square test of dependency technique was applied in analyzing the hypotheses.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: What is the exposure level of Abakaliki residents to information about COVID-19 outbreak?

Figure 1: COVID-19 Outbreak Awareness Media Campaigns

The data indicated that 95.5% of the respondents have high awareness level of COVID-19 media campaigns. This indicates that the COVID-19 media campaign awareness level of the Abakaliki residents' seems to be relatively high. These findings were also corroborated by the data collected from the interview section of the study. The aforementioned findings of this study happened to be in conformity with the findings of Nwamuo (2008) on "Assessment of Anambra Ministry of Health's Campaign on the Malaria Control Booster Project" which states that success of the campaign hinged on the channels of communication used in both the awareness creation stage and implementation. This, the researcher

concludes, explains why it is necessary to use the multimedia approach in health communication. This finding is also in line with the postulation of Nwuneli, [1984], which stated that "for any meaningful change to take place at the rural areas, a decentralized communication should be adopted".

These findings therefore, imply that to create public awareness, the media must report frequently to ensure media use. In the other way round, it can be assumed that every average man on earth can listen to radio or television and grab information.

Research Question 2: To what extent did the media messages influence the knowledge of Abakaliki residents on COVID-19 Outbreak?

Figure 2: COVID-19 Awareness through Media Campaigns

The analysis of research question two revealed that 86.1% respondents have high knowledge level of COVID-19 media campaigns. This indicated that the knowledge level of Abakaliki residents are high. This is in line with the findings of Duru, Eke, Ifeadike, Diwe, Uwakwe, Nwosu, and Chineke in 2014 titled “Antenatal Care Services Utilization among Women of Reproductive Age in Urban and Rural Communities of South East Nigeria: A Comparative Study”, which found that the average month at booking for antenatal care in the health centers was higher in the rural areas (5.2 months) when compared to the urban (4.4) months, with more respondents in the urban areas booking earlier

(P=0.000). More respondents in the urban, 140 (50.8%), attended ANC up to 4 times when compared to their rural counterparts, 102(37.0%) (p= 0.000). Women in the urban areas were more likely to have deliveries supervised by skilled birth attendants (p= 0.000).

The implication of this is that the respondents have high knowledge of COVID-19 media campaigns, by this, their attitude could be influenced.

Research Question 3: What is the level at which the media influenced the attitudes of Abakaliki residents toward COVID-19 Outbreak?

Table 1: Mean Score of the Media Influence of the Abakaliki Residents Attitude Towards COVID-19 Outbreak

	Mean	SD	N	DF	Sign.	T-Cal	T-Crit	Decision
Influenced Attitude	3.8	0.4	385	28	0.05	0.91	1.96	Agree
Not Influenced Attitude	1.7	0.5						Disagree

Source: Field Survey 2021

In responding to this research question, it was revealed that 58.3% respondents have been influenced to a large extent by the campaigns on COVID-19. In summary, majority of the respondents think that as a result of the campaigns against COVID-19, they can change some of their attitude like, avoid the eating of rat meat, and consumption of contaminated fruits or seeds. This finding is further supported by the qualitative data generated through the in-depth interviews done in the metropolis. The qualitative data generated here gave support to the quantitative data above by agreeing that the media campaigns on the prevention of COVID-19 virus influenced the respondents' attitude greatly within these periods. This is in line with the postulation of

Walter Lippmann who said that the mass media put picture in our mind Walter Lippmann, [1922]. Also, the result is in line with the attitude change theory which formed the bed rock of this work. The implication of this finding is that knowledge level of media campaigns seem to have improved over time that it can induce the necessary anticipated required attitude. Thus, there is no doubt that whatever someone has already formed as an attitude may be difficult to change if been required to

Research Question 4: To what extent did the media messages on COVID-19 influence the behaviors of the Abakaliki residents regarding the virus?

Table 1: Mean Score of the Media Influence of the Abakiliki Residents Behavior Towards COVID-19 Outbreak

	Mean	SD	N	DF	Sign.	T-Cal	T-Crit	Decision
Influenced Behaviour	4.3	0.5	385	28	0.05	0.91	1.96	Agree
Not Influenced Behaviour	2.5	0.5						Disagree

Source: Field Survey 2021

Data analysed show that (52.3%) respondents have had their practices influenced to a large extent by the campaigns on COVID-19 virus. In this case, the influence in residents' behaviour is high because most people do consider the dangers in the information made available on the COVID-19 campaigns especially when an individual decides to eat rats meat or consume fruits without washing them.

This finding can be related to the findings of Roeland Monasch entitled "Study on Public Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices Relating to Ebola Virus Disease (EVD) Prevention and Medical Care in Sierra Leone: 2014. From Reoland's study, the Ebola Virus Disease awareness is high, but denial or prevention is low due to the beliefs and practices of the people. The people did not perceive Ebola to be as deadly as it is said and so never influenced their practices.

Test of Hypotheses

The test of hypothesis one, which looked at the significant relationship between the frequency of Abakaliki residents' exposure to media messages on

COVID-19 outbreak and their knowledge of the symptoms of the virus indicated that calculated value of 6.29 is greater than the table value 5.991 at 0.05 error limit. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate is accepted. Therefore, "the knowledge level of Abakaliki residents is dependent on the level of awareness about the disease".

The test of hypothesis two, which looked at the significant relationship between the Abakaliki residents' positive knowledge toward the COVID-19 Virus and their positive attitude indicated that calculated value of 11.61 is greater than the table value 5.991 at 0.05 error limit. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate is accepted. Therefore, "there is a significant relationship between the Abakaliki residents' positive knowledge toward the COVID-19 Virus and their positive attitude.

The test of hypothesis three, which looked at the significant relationship between the Abakaliki residents' positive attitude towards the COVID-19 virus and their positive practice indicated that calculated value of 38.04

is greater than the table value 11.070 at 0.05 error limit. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate is accepted. Therefore, “there is a significant relationship between the Abakaliki residents’ positive attitude toward the COVID-19 Virus campaigns and their positive practice.

Summary of Findings

i. From the study, it was observed that Abakaliki residents exposure to media messages on COVID-19 Outbreak were very frequent and high. The media thrived in its developmental functions of enlightening the general public on the outbreak of the virus, its mode of contraction, transmission and prevention, etc.

ii. That the mass media COVID-19 awareness, positively influenced the knowledge level of the Abakaliki residents on COVID-19 Outbreak.

iii. The result shows that the level at which the media influenced the attitudes of Abakaliki residents toward COVID-19 Outbreak is significantly high. It was also observed that the media have been objective in its surveillance campaign against COVID-19.

iv. Data also revealed that 50.9% respondents have had their practices influenced to a large extent by the campaigns.

Conclusion

A development conscious society must ensure linkage between the process of development and the people’s perception of the activities of the media. In ensuring the linkage, it is important and in fact, necessary to discover whether a good number of the population is sufficiently exposed to the media and is capable of making productive use of media messages.

In view of the findings, it can be concluded that the media have made significant contribution in the campaign against COVID-19 outbreak in Nigeria and can stand firm as the best platform to champion development at all quarters of the society. The fact remains that the media carry the greater responsibility for providing awareness and education about our pluralist political life. Mass media are the effective means of

enlightening the public on the war against global health challenges.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend that:

i. That the media should step up their efforts in their campaign against COVID-19 in Ebonyi State.

ii. The International organization such (WHO) should also intensify efforts towards enlightening the masses on the mode of prevention of COVID-19 outbreak in Nigeria, special interest should be given to the hinter lands.

iii. The media have important roles to play by seeking to enlighten the public on the mode of prevention of COVID-19 in Nigeria.

iv. COVID-19 is still endemic in Nigeria. The primary care health worker in a rural area is the one most likely to be the first point of call for persons seeking western medicine. It is therefore essential that he is adequately informed about the disease, its presentation and prevention, so that he can not only protect himself, but prevent spread within the community.

v. The Radio should strive to break through developmental barriers with great determination, perseverance, unbreakable solidarity and genuine desires to conquer the natural the negative perception of the public on the COVID-19.

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